

**Essential Obstetric Care in Timor-Leste:
The Shape of Safe Motherhood in a Developing Country.**

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Archival Summary

This document is a preserved, citable edition of research originally completed in **March 2011**, examining the provision of **Essential Obstetric Care (EOC)** in Timor-Leste. It investigates the high burden of maternal mortality, gaps in emergency obstetric services, and the structural barriers impacting access — including geographic isolation, health workforce shortages, limited financing, and cultural considerations.

The study reviews:

- Availability and distribution of Basic and Comprehensive Emergency Obstetric Care facilities
- Policy alignment with the **Millennium Development Goals**
- Comparative maternal health indicators in the region
- Strategies for improving equitable access to life-saving services

This archival edition preserves the original content — including data, analysis, and recommendations — as a permanent scholarly record. It is presented here in a DOI-ready format to ensure long-term citation and accessibility.

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Introduction

The challenge of enabling safe motherhood in Timor-Leste is significant. In a developing country ravaged by war and the struggle for independence, Essential Obstetric Care (EOC), by western standards, is scantily provided. The magnitude of maternal mortality is very high, with one in thirty-five women having a lifetime risk of obstetric death. As with many developing countries, inequalities in maternal health is a function of social, cultural and contextual factors, extending past health services to policy making, education, economics and beyond. This paper will analyse the provision of Essential Obstetric Care in Timor-Leste, the barriers to supply, and make suggestions for improvement given current constraints.

Provision of Essential Obstetric Care in Timor-Leste

Timor-Leste comprises four islands and a population of approximately 1.1 million.^[i] According to *The Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste Health Profile, August 2002*, the following distribution of health professionals provides services to the people of Timor-Leste: 47 physicians (12 national and 35 international), 624 nurses and 226 midwives. With only one tertiary level health facility and poor primary care, the lack of EOC and Emergency Obstetric Care (EmOC) has led to an extremely high Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) estimated to be 660 deaths per every 100,000 births.^[ii]

The prevailing causes of maternal mortality in Timor-Leste include haemorrhage, sepsis, unsafe abortion, obstructed labour and hypertensive diseases of pregnancy. Indirect causes include increasing incidence of teenage pregnancy and early marriage, geographic isolation, poor reproductive health, low maternal literacy/education rates, prevalence of acute infectious diseases such as malaria, and chronic disease states such as malnutrition and anaemia.^[iii] All are exacerbated by the many social, economic, geographic and political factors underpinning and in some cases, obstructing change.

With the instigation of the Timorese Ministry of Health in 2001, and the subsequent adoption of the Millennium Development Goals, several key areas of deficit were identified that directly relate to the provision of EOC and maternal health outcomes.

The following objectives were defined:

- ∅ the reduction of maternal and infant mortality;
- ∅ the improvement of reproductive health;
- ∅ equity of access to health services;
- ∅ provision of a regulated minimum healthcare service;
- ∅ increased health literacy for women, (including access to information); and
- ∅ improvement in the nutritional status of mothers and children.^[iv]

Timor-Leste Ministry of Health Millennium Development Goals

Reduce MMR by 75% between 1990 and 2015

INDICATORS	2001	MDG TARGET 2015
MMR per 100,000 live births	240-800	252
Proportion of births attended by skilled personnel	24%-38%	60%

EOC in Timor-Leste: Current Service Provision and Coverage

The physical infrastructure for health services delivery is extremely limited throughout Timor-Leste. The only tertiary level referral hospital, located in Baucau, provides 114 beds and has the capacity to provide surgery with general anaesthesia. Four regional hospitals of 24 beds serve the districts of Cavalima, Bobonaro, Oecusse and Ainaro. Basic inpatient services are provided. Surgery is not yet available. All other districts provide community centres with the capacity to offer basic health services and to deploy mobile clinics. These centres are termed 'level one' health facilities and cover a four to eight kilometre radius. They provide basic non-diagnostic curative consultation, antenatal and postnatal care, immunization, infant growth monitoring, and health promotion.

Community health centre facilities (level two) exist at the sub-district level for the provision of health promotion, prevention, and out-patient curative consultations. Services are supported by a simple laboratory. Level three healthcare facilities are located in the districts bordering Dili, Aielu and Liquica. This level of healthcare facility has the additional capacity of basic Emergency Obstetric Care (EmOC), with procedures such as forceps or vacuum assisted delivery, manual removal of placenta, and treatment of other obstetric complications.

Inpatient facilities for up to 20 beds are located in five districts, providing level 4 services such as minor surgery not requiring general anaesthesia. These facilities provide diagnostic medical consultation and referral where appropriate, medical pathology and other support diagnostics.^[v]

EOC Coverage

According to the *Timor-Leste Health Statistics Report*, skilled health personnel attend only 27.2% of all births. Use of modern methods of contraception is very low at <7% of the married population of reproductive age, and the development of a nationwide family planning programme is still at policy development stage.

Rural isolation means inequitable and problematic access to antenatal care, skilled birth attendants, EOC and EmOC for many Timorese women. Accessibility is greatly reduced by geographic isolation with only 27% of Timorese living in urban areas and the remainder living in rural villages.^[vi] The population resides primarily on one half of the major island, East Timor, however there are also residents on three other remote islands who receive little

to no EOC services. Access issues are central to reducing the MMR and to providing better coverage and EOC service provision.

Barriers to coverage

The provision of EOC services across Timor-Leste is a challenge. Indonesian occupation since 1975 and subsequent recognition of self-determination by the United Nations in 2002 has left Timor-Leste struggling with post-crisis development. Tax revenue insufficiency linked to low GDP per capita means a meagre base from which to redistribute wealth. Public goods such as health care receive too few dollars to address needs. A policy re-prioritisation matched by adequate funding will make the difference in the short term. For increased capacity and long term change, economic growth, stewardship and outsourcing are required.

The ongoing problem of refugees in Timor-Leste persists. Itinerant populations provide particular problems in EOC service delivery. They are difficult to reach for educational and preventative care purposes and provide ongoing primary and antenatal care difficulties due to the nomadic behaviour of internally displaced persons (IDP). Issues of equitable distribution are poorly addressed and becoming more important as IDPs return to their pre-war homes. Their migration brings an increase in service demand in remote areas and staffing these areas is problematic with midwives reluctant to service communities without utilities and basic infrastructure such as communications.

Cultural perceptions affect penetration of available services in Timor-Leste further complicating EOC service provision. Many perceive the use of medical facilities for child birth as constituting failure on behalf of the mother. Consequently, Timorese women do not routinely seek EOC, and only seek EmOC when in a critical condition.

Fifty-two percent of Timorese are illiterate and health literacy is poor. Ignorance of modern methods affects utilization of available EOC services. A reduction in maternal morbidity and mortality will be greatly facilitated by a non-didactic, culturally sensitive, continuous, female friendly, educational campaign that directly targets women of reproductive age and puberty.

Pregnant Timorese married to economic migrants often feel isolated and vulnerable away from their maternal families. The tendency for women (particularly *primigravidae*) to attempt to return to their home village prior to delivery also sees many travelling long distances leaving areas of high service provision to arrive in areas of low service provision. The women often work as long as possible, travelling late in the third trimester, often unaided and without the care of a primary physician or midwife should difficulties arise.

Barriers to EOC Service Provision

By far, the greatest barrier to EOC service provision is lack of funds. Healthcare financing requires responsible and informed economic management by the government of Timor-Leste and recognition that as a public good, health care has associated externalities and failures that need to be addressed. This is a key role of government – to provide essential services where the allocative power of competitive markets fails. In collaboration with

partner organisations, (NGOs and donor funding), the reliance on out of pocket funding as a dominant source of health financing can be minimised. This is especially important for Timor-Leste as the burden of out of pocket costs falls heaviest on the poor, and serves as a barrier and disincentive to consumption of health care services.

Given that healthcare the world over is predicated on the problem of infinite need and scarce resources, the use of evidence based investment is critical. Policy grounded in the criteria of efficiency, equity and effectiveness must be paramount if dollars and morals are not to be squandered. The current capacity of the government of Timor-Leste to respond to public health concerns is minimal and as a result, initiatives and development in public health, particularly broad primary health care measures such as EOC policy reform, are limited in their application and effectiveness. If Timor-Leste is to achieve the Millennium Development Goals then collaboration with external partners is essential.

Barriers to EOC Service Provision: The Economic Realities

Government health expenditure per capita is very low, ranking 141st lowest out of the 193 World Health Organisation (WHO) member nations.^[vii] Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) for health expenditure as a function of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) illustrates per capita expenditure of US\$109 per annum. Total health expenditure as a percentage of GDP is 17.7%. Such constrained expenditure despite high proportion of GDP directly correlates with low income per capita and low Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Efficiency, Effectiveness and Equity

Health care in Timor-Leste lacks both technical and allocative efficiency. The ineffective provision of EOC is endemic. The number of trained health care professionals is insufficient for the population, and their distribution is highly concentrated to major urban centres leaving the majority of the population, rural dwelling Timorese, to fend for themselves. EOC services are out of date, fail to meet evidence based criteria, and consistently employ antiquated methods due to insufficient resources and capital; physical, human and monetary. Existing EOC is ineffectual in meeting the needs of the population.

Efficient EOC services depend on the availability of basic EOC drugs, serviceable equipment, consumables, staffing and infrastructure. Shortages of all are widespread in fixed healthcare facilities and mobile services. These inadequacies prevent the delivery of evidence based EOC and EmOC services.

Gender inequalities exist in the form of non-prioritised health services for women, women of remote areas, and women of low educational status. The disempowerment of women means women seek health care, food and entitlements last. Little to no political power or influence over policy direction consolidates this position at an individual, community and national level.

Currently, there are no indigenous obstetricians in Timor-Leste and the country depends on the services of expatriate specialists. It is questionable whether the development of ongoing effective EOC/EmOC services is possible given the current Timorese educational priorities.

There is an inequitable education of females and educated males often seek better employment opportunities abroad. Women tend to have greater ties to their country and region of birth and if educated, could contribute substantially to the local labour market. A role for development partners may be to facilitate training in obstetrics/gynaecology for the provision of EOC at a primary health level and EmOC at hospitals, as well as counsellors for family planning.

Future Directions: What can be done to improve EOC in Timor-Leste?

Policy is central to achieving better health outcomes and efficient EOC services. Appropriate and equitable EOC interventions need to reach underserved and vulnerable women as a first priority to save lives. This requires political commitment and equitable representation for maternal health in federal budgets. Urgent action is imperative. Technology is not the constraint in the provision of health services such as EOC, demand and supply side policy is, and existing proven practices and tools must be up-scaled and implemented immediately. Disadvantaging women is a force multiplier for the rest of society and there is a well demonstrated relationship between maternal and child health outcomes. Ministers must learn to view health as an asset model, not a deficit model, whereby timely and proactive investment contributes to the social and economic prosperity of all.

There must be wider strengthening of the health care system and developmental stewardship with collaboration partners will help this to progress. Excellent economic management is essential and supply must be at the lowest possible cost. Gap analysis linked to targeted investment can align science with cost and predict outcomes for investment dollars. Marginal budgeting for bottlenecks will address gaps and barriers in the market. While government must ensure affordability, manage competition, provide cost containment and ensure equity, the tax revenue base must also be increased. Sin taxes and foreign owned companies can help relieve reliance on donor funding as will private/social health insurance once developed and promoted.

To meet the twin objectives of efficiency and equity, it is not enough to rely on the macro-economics; the sources of inequity must be identified and addressed through policy. These are the external factors affecting health care - culture, geography, gender, education, social capital, employment, socio-economic status and empowerment all affect the demand and provision of EOC services in Timor-Leste. In moderating the drivers of health care costs, the government needs to address the education of all in family planning and health care. No up-front fees and low out of pocket costs are vital to ensure the poor are able to access services, and use of EOC needs to be promoted to the vulnerable at the community level. Universal attendance by a skilled birth attendant must be a nationwide priority.

It is important for policy makers to realise that equity and efficiency can occur together. Health metrics such as the National Health Accounts (NHA) are vital tools to inform priorities through data. They are indispensable for quantification of health effects and the use of population modelling to determine cost effectiveness. It is essential that Timor-Leste facilitate the collection and release of such data so that health economic evaluation can be used in decision making. Accurate and up to date statistics on risk factors

and diseases are required to formulate policy and measure change. In the absence of data, the burden of disease and response to policy changes cannot be effectively evaluated.

Nationally, work is progressing to improve EOC in Timor-Leste. Training of midwives has commenced at Timor-Leste's first dedicated midwifery facility. While it is proving difficult to increase the proportion of births attended by skilled personnel, an incremental approach will assist. It is salutary to note the lessons of Nepal in 2001-2006. With a skilled birth attendant presence of only 18%, in a disrupted health system working at capacity, attention was instead directed towards improving women's literacy, legalisation of abortion and empowerment of women. The result was a drop in the MMR by almost half (539 deaths per 100,000 live births in 2001 to 281 in 2006), fall in the total fertility rate, increase in women's literacy and empowerment, and increased use of family planning services.^[viii] All achieved without changing the number of births attended by skilled personnel and minimal funding.

The lessons of Nepal demonstrate that a successful approach does not necessarily mean costly investment in tertiary infrastructure. Increased women's literacy and health promotion is essential to empowerment and progress. It is women who need to take charge of their reproductive life and become champions of the cause if the desired health outcomes are to be achieved. Promoting community involvement at planning, delivery and in ongoing monitoring enables women and ensures their interest and compliance in national priorities.

The Timor-Leste National Safe Motherhood Strategy needs more staff directed towards its completion. Where capital shortages are prohibitive, the government needs to recognise the many benefits partner organisations can offer and utilize them. Small countries frequently lack capacity to reap economies of scale and provide efficient and equitable public goods. Outsourcing workload and exploiting comparative advantage is imperative where domestic capacity lags.

Attention must also be directed beyond the current generation of women requiring EOC to future generations. It is well recognised that many difficulties in childbirth arise from poor nutrition during maternal growth phases and that a life cycle approach is an appropriate contributor to preventative health care and reduction in EmOC demand. Timor-Leste is not a food resource poor country. It has good annual rainfall and a bountiful supply from the sea. None-the-less, there is a high percentage of malnutrition, due in part to ignorance and also from poverty, that leads to general lack of food security and poor nutritional indicators. Ensuring good nutrition through education and supplements where required will enable proper growth and birthing ability for women of subsequent generations.

Conclusion

Health is a human right and essential obstetric care is a fundamental part of ensuring health for women and children. To remedy the poor outcomes in maternal health, Timor-Leste must address both the technical and allocative inefficiencies that have given rise to an inequitable provision of EOC services and increase provision and demand for services through targeted cost effective programmes. Macro-economic policy must focus on growth and development to support GDP and the provision of health care, and policy in all sectors

must drive changes to prioritize maternal health particularly for the vulnerable and underserved.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Websites:

World Health Organisation, The Partnership for Maternal, Newborn and Child Health, http://www.who.int/pmnch/activities/human_resources/healthcareprofessionals/en/index11.html

Accessed 12 October, 2010.

World Health Organisation, Maternal and Newborn Health: Making Pregnancy Safer – Assessment Tool for the Quality of Hospital Care for Mothers and Newborn

Babies, https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0008/98792/E93128.pdf

Accessed October 15th, 2010.

World Health Organisation, Timor-Leste: National Health System

Profile <http://searo.who.int/EN/Section313/Section1526.htm>, Accessed October, 2010.

World Health Organisation, Making Pregnancy

Safer, <http://www.searo.who.int/en/Section13/section2364.htm>

Accessed October 21st, 2010.

World Health Organisation, Global Health

Observatory <http://apps.who.int/ghodata/?vid=19600>

Accessed October 20th, 2010.

World Health Organisation, Timor-Leste: National Expenditure On Health,

(USD). <https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http://www.who.int/entity/nha/country/tls.pdf>

World Health Organisation, <http://www.who.int/topics/pregnancy/en/>

Accessed October 15-31, 2010.

World Health Organisation, Making Pregnancy

Safer, <http://www.who.int/topics/pregnancy/en/> Accessed October 15-31, 2010.

OECD (November 2009), OECD Health Data 2009 - Frequently Requested Data, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

http://www.oecd.org/document/16/0,3343,en_2649_34631_2085200_1_1_1_1,00.html

Accessed 23.3.10

World Health Organisation (May 2009), World Health Statistics 2009, World Health

Organization. <http://www.who.int/whosis/whostat/2009/en/index.html> Accessed 23.3.10

“How gender inequalities impact on the achievement of MDG 4 and 5.” World Health Organisation

<http://www.euro.who.int/en/what-we-do/health-topics/Life-stages/maternal-and-newborn-health/news/news3/2010/12/progress-regarding-mdgs-3,-4-and-5.-draft-conclusions-from-who-meeting-of-national-focal-points-for-family-and-community-health-in-durres,-albania>.

Accessed 12.10.10

A Comprehensive Approach

Required, <http://www.australianvolunteers.com/volunteer/volunteer-stories/a-comprehensive-approach-required.aspx>

Accessed 12 October, 2010.

Global Health Observatory, Indicator Statistics, <http://apps.who.int/ghodata/?vid=19600#>, Accessed October, 2010.

List of countries by total health expenditure (PPP) per capita, World Health Organisation (2006, 2009) 10

<https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http://www.who.int/entity/nha/country/tls.pdf>
Accessed 12 October, 2010.

Alonso A, Brugha R: Rehabilitating the health system after conflict in East Timor: a shift from NGO to government leadership, *Health Policy and Planning* 2006., 21(3)

Official Government Portal of Timor-Leste, <http://timor-leste.gov.tl/?lang=en>
Accessed 1-31 October, 2010.

SEARO

<http://www.searo.who.int/en/Section13/section2364.htm>

Accessed October, 2010.

Books:

Acton, H.B., **The Morals of Markets and Related Essays**, 1993.

McTaggart, D., Findlay, C., & Parkin, M., **Macroeconomics**, 1992.

Donaldson and Gerard, **Economics of Health Care Financing: The Visible Hand**, 2004.

Eugene Braunwald, Stephen L. Hauser, Anthony S. Fauci, Dennis L. Kasper, Dan L. Longo, and Larry Jameson [Eds], **Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine**, 15th Ed, McGraw-Hill, 2001.

Post Graduate Subject Reading Lists:

Maternal and Child Health in Developing Countries (2010)

Centre For International Health - Curtin University

International Health and Primary Health Care (2010)

Centre For International Health - Curtin University

Economics of Health Financing (2011)

Centre For International Health - Curtin University

Journal Articles:

Performance Contracting: Achieving the twin objectives of efficiency and equity, Bushan et al, **Asian Development Bank**, (2002).

World Health Organisation, Health Related Millennium Development Goals,

https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http://www.who.int/entity/whosis/whostat/EN_WHS10_Part1.pdf.

Making stillbirths count, making numbers talk - issues in data collection for stillbirths.

Frøen JF, Gordijn SJ, Abdel-Aleem H, Bergsjø P, Betran A, Duke CW, Fauveau V, Flenady V, Hinderaker SG, Hofmeyr GJ, Jokhio AH, Lawn J, Lumbiganon P, Merialdi M, Pattinson R, Shankar A.

BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 Dec 17;9:58.

Delivering interventions to reduce the global burden of stillbirths: improving service supply and community demand.

Bhutta ZA, Darmstadt GL, Haws RA, Yakoob MY, Lawn JE.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 May 7;9 Suppl 1:S7. Review.

Global report on preterm birth and stillbirth (1 of 7): definitions, description of the burden and opportunities to improve data.

Lawn JE, Gravett MG, Nunes TM, Rubens CE, Stanton C; GAPPS Review Group.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2010 Feb 23;10 Suppl 1:S1.

Four million neonatal deaths: counting and attribution of cause of death.

Lawn JE, Osrin D, Adler A, Cousens S.
Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol. 2008 Sep;22(5):410-6.

Reducing stillbirths: behavioural and nutritional interventions before and during pregnancy.

Yakoob MY, Menezes EV, Soomro T, Haws RA, Darmstadt GL, Bhutta ZA.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 May 7;9 Suppl 1:S3. Review.

3.2 million stillbirths: epidemiology and overview of the evidence review.

Lawn JE, Yakoob MY, Haws RA, Soomro T, Darmstadt GL, Bhutta ZA.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 May 7;9 Suppl 1:S2.

[Can implementation of intensified perinatal survey be effective in improving the quality of perinatal care?].

Troszyński M.
Med Wieku Rozwoj. 2010 Apr-Jun;14(2):138-49. Polish.

Reducing stillbirths: screening and monitoring during pregnancy and labour.

Haws RA, Yakoob MY, Soomro T, Menezes EV, Darmstadt GL, Bhutta ZA.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 May 7;9 Suppl 1:S5. Review.

Reducing stillbirths: interventions during labour.

Darmstadt GL, Yakoob MY, Haws RA, Menezes EV, Soomro T, Bhutta ZA.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 May 7;9 Suppl 1:S6. Review.

Reducing stillbirths: prevention and management of medical disorders and infections during pregnancy.

Menezes EV, Yakoob MY, Soomro T, Haws RA, Darmstadt GL, Bhutta ZA.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 May 7;9 Suppl 1:S4.

Stillbirth rates: delivering estimates in 190 countries.

Stanton C, Lawn JE, Rahman H, Wilczynska-Ketende K, Hill K.
Lancet. 2006 May 6;367(9521):1487-94. Review.

Commentary: reducing the world's stillbirths.

Goldenberg RL, McClure EM, Belizán JM.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 May 7;9 Suppl 1:S1.

Using active birth defects surveillance programs to supplement data on fetal death reports: improving surveillance data on stillbirths.

Duke W, Williams L, Correa A.

Birth Defects Res A Clin Mol Teratol. 2008 Nov;82(11):799-804.

Global report on preterm birth and stillbirth (2 of 7): discovery science.

Gravett MG, Rubens CE, Nunes TM; GAPPS Review Group.

BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2010 Feb 23;10 Suppl 1:S2.

Changes in the registration of stillbirths < 500 g in Canada, 1985-95. Fetal-Infant Mortality Study Group of the Canadian Perinatal Surveillance System.

Joseph KS, Allen A, Kramer MS, Cyr M, Fair M.

Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol. 1999 Jul;13(3):278-87.

Medical causes on stillbirth certificates in England and Wales: distribution and results of hierarchical classifications tested by the Office for National Statistics.

Alberman E, Blatchley N, Botting B, Schuman J, Dunn A.

Br J Obstet Gynaecol. 1997 Sep;104(9):1043-9.

Assessing quality of obstetric care for low-risk deliveries; methodological problems in the use of population based mortality data.

Moster D, Markestad T, Lie RT.

Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand. 2000 Jun;79(6):478-84.

Classification of perinatal deaths.

Wigglesworth JS.

Soz Praventivmed. 1994;39(1):11-4.

Classification and analysis of fetal deaths in Massachusetts.

Lammer EJ, Brown LE, Anderka MT, Guyer B.

JAMA. 1989 Mar 24-31;261(12):1757-62.

Stillbirth in developing countries: a review of causes, risk factors and prevention strategies.

McClure EM, Saleem S, Pasha O, Goldenberg RL.

J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med. 2009 Mar;22(3):183-90. Review.

Global report on preterm birth and stillbirth (6 of 7): ethical considerations.

Kelley M, Rubens CE; GAPPS Review Group.

BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2010 Feb 23;10 Suppl 1:S6. Review.

Population-based recurrence risk of sudden infant death syndrome compared with other infant and fetal deaths.

Oyen N, Skjaerven R, Irgens LM.

Am J Epidemiol. 1996 Aug 1;144(3):300-5.

A comparison of the Perinatal Society of Australia and New Zealand-Perinatal Death Classification system and relevant condition at death stillbirth classification systems.

Lu JR, McCowan L.

Aust N Z J Obstet Gynaecol. 2009 Oct;49(5):467-71.

Avoidable stillbirths and neonatal deaths in rural Tanzania.

Hinderaker SG, Olsen BE, Bergsjø PB, Gasheka P, Lie RT, Havnen J, Kvåle G.

BJOG. 2003 Jun;110(6):616-23.

Mortality by cause for eight regions of the world: Global Burden of Disease Study.

Murray CJ, Lopez AD.

Lancet. 1997 May 3;349(9061):1269-76.

Classification of stillbirth by relevant condition at death (ReCoDe): population based cohort study.

Gardosi J, Kady SM, McGeown P, Francis A, Tonks A.

BMJ. 2005 Nov 12;331(7525):1113-7. Epub 2005 Oct 19.

A computer-based method for cause of death classification in stillbirths and neonatal deaths.

Winbo IG, Serenius FH, Dahlquist GG, Källén BA.

Int J Epidemiol. 1997 Dec;26(6):1298-306.

Prospective community-based cluster census and case-control study of stillbirths and neonatal deaths in the West Bank and Gaza Strip.

Kalter HD, Khazen RR, Barghouthi M, Odeh M.

Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol. 2008 Jul;22(4):321-33.

[The quality of registration of causes of death in perinatal and neonatal deaths]

Andersen KV, Helweg-Larsen K, Lange AP.

Ugeskr Laeger. 1991 May 27;153(22):1577-81. Danish.

Regional differences in stillbirth and neonatal death rate in Sweden with a cause-of-death specific analysis.

Serenius F, Winbo I, Dahlquist G, Källén B.

Acta Paediatr. 2001 Sep;90(9):1062-7.

Perinatal deaths in a Norwegian county 1986-96 classified by the Nordic-Baltic perinatal classification: geographical contrasts as a basis for quality assessment.

Holt J, Vold IN, Odland JO, Førde OH.

Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand. 2000 Feb;79(2):107-12.

Aetiology of stillbirths and neonatal deaths in rural Ghana: implications for health programming in developing countries.

Edmond KM, Quigley MA, Zandoh C, Danso S, Hurt C, Owusu Agyei S, Kirkwood BR.

Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol. 2008 Sep;22(5):430-7.

Diagnostic accuracy of verbal autopsies in ascertaining the causes of stillbirths and neonatal deaths in rural Ghana.

Edmond KM, Quigley MA, Zandoh C, Danso S, Hurt C, Owusu Agyei S, Kirkwood BR.
Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol. 2008 Sep;22(5):417-29.

Causes of death and associated conditions (Codac): a utilitarian approach to the classification of perinatal deaths.

Frøen JF, Pinar H, Flenady V, Bahrin S, Charles A, Chauke L, Day K, Duke CW, Facchinetti F, Fretts RC, Gardener G, Gilshenan K, Gordijn SJ, Gordon A, Guyon G, Harrison C, Koshy R, Pattinson RC, Petersson K, Russell L, Saastad E, Smith GC, Torabi R.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 Jun 10;9:22.

NICE, a new cause of death classification for stillbirths and neonatal deaths. Neonatal and Intrauterine Death Classification according to Etiology.

Winbo IG, Serenius FH, Dahlquist GG, Källén BA.
Int J Epidemiol. 1998 Jun;27(3):499-504.

Registration of vital data: are live births and stillbirths comparable all over Europe?

Gourbin G, Masuy-Stroobant G.
Bull World Health Organ. 1995;73(4):449-60.

Effect of changing the stillbirth definition on evaluation of perinatal mortality rates.

Cartlidge PH, Stewart JH.
Lancet. 1995 Aug 19;346(8973):486-8.

Analysis of stillbirths in a Nigerian mission hospital.

Onyiriuka AN.
Nig Q J Hosp Med. 2009 Jan-Mar;19(1):27-31.

Rates, timing and causes of neonatal deaths in rural India: implications for neonatal health programmes.

Baqui AH, Darmstadt GL, Williams EK, Kumar V, Kiran TU, Panwar D, Srivastava VK, Ahuja R, Black RE, Santosham M.
Bull World Health Organ. 2006 Sep;84(9):706-13.

Perinatal mortality in Taiwan.

Wang PD, Lin RS.
Public Health. 1999 Jan;113(1):27-33.

[Discrepancy between results of registration of perinatal cause of death by the CBS (Central Bureau of Statistics) and by personal studies in the Delft-Westland-Oostland region]

de Galan-Roosen AE, Kuijpers JC, Oei YB, van Velzen D, Mackenbach JP.
Ned Tijdschr Geneeskd. 1997 Feb 1;141(5):237-40. Dutch.

Global and regional causes of death.

Mathers CD, Boerma T, Ma Fat D.
Br Med Bull. 2009;92:7-32. Epub . Review.

The role of reviews of perinatal deaths.

King JF, Warren RA.

Semin Fetal Neonatal Med. 2006 Apr;11(2):79-87. Epub 2006 Jan 9.

Cesarean section on request at 39 weeks: impact on shoulder dystocia, fetal trauma, neonatal encephalopathy, and intrauterine fetal demise.

Hankins GD, Clark SM, Munn MB.

Semin Perinatol. 2006 Oct;30(5):276-87. Review.

The measurement and monitoring of surgical adverse events.

Bruce J, Russell EM, Mollison J, Krukowski ZH.

Health Technol Assess. 2001;5(22):1-194. Review.

Changing patterns of perinatal and infant mortality in Western Australia: implications for prevention.

Stanley FJ, Waddell VP.

Med J Aust. 1985 Oct 28;143(9):379-81.

Causes of stillbirths and early neonatal deaths: data from 7993 pregnancies in six developing countries.

Ngoc NT, Merialdi M, Abdel-Aleem H, Carroli G, Purwar M, Zavaleta N, Campódonico L, Ali MM, Hofmeyr GJ, Mathai M, Lincetto O, Villar J.

Bull World Health Organ. 2006 Sep;84(9):699-705

Registration of births, stillbirths and infant deaths in Jamaica.

McCaw-Binns AM, Fox K, Foster-Williams KE, Ashley DE, Irons B.

Int J Epidemiol. 1996 Aug;25(4):807-13.

A new system for determining the causes of stillbirth.

Dudley DJ, Goldenberg R, Conway D, Silver RM, Saade GR, Varner MW, Pinar H, Coustan D, Bukowski R, Stoll B, Koch MA, Parker CB, Reddy UM; Stillbirth Research Collaborative Network.

Obstet Gynecol. 2010 Aug;116(2 Pt 1):254-60.

Counting the dead and what they died from: an assessment of the global status of cause of death data.

Mathers CD, Fat DM, Inoue M, Rao C, Lopez AD.

Bull World Health Organ. 2005 Mar;83(3):171-7. Epub 2005 Mar 16.

Etiology and prevention of stillbirth.

Fretts RC.

Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2005 Dec;193(6):1923-35. Review.

Social deprivation and the causes of stillbirth and infant mortality.

Guildea ZE, Fone DL, Dunstan FD, Sibert JR, Cartlidge PH.

Arch Dis Child. 2001 Apr;84(4):307-10.

Analysis of birthweight and gestational age in antepartum stillbirths.

Gardosi J, Mul T, Mongelli M, Fagan D.
Br J Obstet Gynaecol. 1998 May;105(5):524-30.

Newborn survival in low resource settings--are we delivering?

Lawn JE, Kerber K, Enweronu-Laryea C, Masee Bateman O.
BJOG. 2009 Oct;116 Suppl 1:49-59. Review.

No cry at birth: global estimates of intrapartum stillbirths and intrapartum-related neonatal deaths.

Lawn J, Shibuya K, Stein C.
Bull World Health Organ. 2005 Jun;83(6):409-17. Epub 2005 Jun 17.

Declining autopsy rates in stillbirths and infant deaths: results from Funen County, Denmark, 1986-96.

Kock KF, Vestergaard V, Hardt-Madsen M, Garne E.
J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med. 2003 Jun;13(6):403-7.

Rates of perinatal mortality and low birth weight among 3367 consecutive births in south of Beirut.

Bittar Z.
J Med Liban. 1998 May-Jun;46(3):126-30.

Analysis of perinatal mortality and its components: time for a change?

Kramer MS, Liu S, Luo Z, Yuan H, Platt RW, Joseph KS; Fetal and Infant Health Study Group of the Canadian Perinatal Surveillance System.
Am J Epidemiol. 2002 Sep 15;156(6):493-7.

Classification and description of stillbirths in New South Wales, 2002-2004.

Gordon A, Jeffery HE.
Med J Aust. 2008 Jun 2;188(11):645-8.

[Stillbirths in Ile-et-Vilaine]

Sénécal J, Roussey M, Dubois J, Debroise C, Le Marec B, Delahaye M, Morellec J, Jouan H.
Arch Fr Pediatr. 1989 Feb;46(2):143-7. French.

An audit and trends of perinatal mortality at the Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi.

Korejo R, Bhutta S, Noorani KJ, Bhutta ZA.
J Pak Med Assoc. 2007 Apr;57(4):168-72.

Confidential enquiry into stillbirths and deaths in infancy.

Jakeman N.
Paediatr Nurs. 1998 Dec-1999 Jan;10(10):6-7.

An evaluation of classification systems for stillbirth.

Flenady V, Frøen JF, Pinar H, Torabi R, Saastad E, Guyon G, Russell L, Charles A, Harrison C, Chauke L, Pattinson R, Koshy R, Bahrin S, Gardener G, Day K, Petersson K, Gordon A, Gilshenan K.
BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2009 Jun 19;9:24.

Confidential Enquiry into Stillbirths and Deaths in Infancy. Highlights of the 5th annual report (I).

Rosser J.
Pract Midwife. 1998 Oct;1(10):32-3. No abstract available.

The Stockholm classification of stillbirth.

Varli IH, Petersson K, Bottinga R, Bremme K, Hofsjö A, Holm M, Holste C, Kublickas M, Norman M, Pilo C, Roos N, Sundberg A, Wolff K, Papadogiannakis N.
Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand. 2008;87(11):1202-12.

Two million intrapartum-related stillbirths and neonatal deaths: where, why, and what can be done?

Lawn JE, Lee AC, Kinney M, Sibley L, Carlo WA, Paul VK, Pattinson R, Darmstadt GL.
Int J Gynaecol Obstet. 2009 Oct;107 Suppl 1:S5-18, S19. Review.

A New South Wales population-based study of stillbirths weighing 2,500 g or more.

Adelson P, Spurrett B, Trudinger B, Frommer M.
Aust N Z J Obstet Gynaecol. 1993 May;33(2):166-73.

Reducing obesity and related chronic disease risk in children and youth: a synthesis of evidence with 'best practice' recommendations.

Flynn MA, McNeil DA, Maloff B, Mutasingwa D, Wu M, Ford C, Tough SC.
Obes Rev. 2006 Feb;7 Suppl 1:7-66. Review.

Estimating population cause-specific mortality fractions from in-hospital mortality: validation of a new method.

Murray CJ, Lopez AD, Barofsky JT, Bryson-Cahn C, Lozano R.
PLoS Med. 2007 Nov 20;4(11):e326.

Rates of and factors associated with delivery-related perinatal death among term infants in Scotland.

Pasupathy D, Wood AM, Pell JP, Fleming M, Smith GC.
JAMA. 2009 Aug 12;302(6):660-8.

[The validity of the certification of natimortality: the experience of a local study]

D'Argenio P, Triassi M, Arsieri R, Pugliese A, D'Armiento M, Russo R, Vecchione R.
Epidemiol Prev. 1995 Sep;19(64):266-9. Italian.

Community-based prevention of perinatal deaths: lessons from nineteenth-century Sweden.

Andersson T, Högberg U, Bergström S.
Int J Epidemiol. 2000 Jun;29(3):542-8.

Swedish maternal mortality in the 19th century by different definitions: previous stillbirths but not multiparity risk factor for maternal death.

Andersson T, Bergström S, Högberg U.
Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand. 2000 Aug;79(8):679-86.

The influence of antenatal and maternal factors on stillbirths and neonatal deaths in New South Wales, Australia.

Mohsin M, Bauman AE, Jalaludin B.
J Biosoc Sci. 2006 Sep;38(5):643-57.

Can child deaths be prevented? The Arizona Child Fatality Review Program experience.

Rimsza ME, Schackner RA, Bowen KA, Marshall W.
Pediatrics. 2002 Jul;110(1 Pt 1):e11

Stillbirth classification--developing an international consensus for research: executive summary of a National Institute of Child Health and Human Development workshop.

Reddy UM, Goldenberg R, Silver R, Smith GC, Pauli RM, Wapner RJ, Gardosi J, Pinar H, Grafe M, Kupfermanc M, Hulthén Varli I, Erwich JJ, Fretts RC, Willinger M.
Obstet Gynecol. 2009 Oct;114(4):901-14. Erratum in: Obstet Gynecol. 2010 Jan;115(1):191.

Perinatal death pattern in the four districts of Thailand: findings from the Prospective Cohort Study of Thai Children (PCTC).

Mo-suwan L, Isaranurug S, Chanvitan P, Techasena W, Sutra S, Supakunpinyo C, Choprapawon C.
J Med Assoc Thai. 2009 May;92(5):660-6.

Reducing perinatal mortality in Vila Central Hospital, Vanuatu.

Maouris P.
P N G Med J. 1994 Sep;37(3):178-80.

Conquering the intolerable burden of malaria: what's new, what's needed: a summary.

Breman JG, Alilio MS, Mills A.
Am J Trop Med Hyg. 2004 Aug;71(2 Suppl):1-15. Review.

The perinatal mortality rate as an indicator of quality of care in international comparisons.

Richardus JH, Graafmans WC, Verloove-Vanhorick SP, Mackenbach JP.
Med Care. 1998 Jan;36(1):54-66.

[Epidemiology of fetal deaths in the Seine-Saint-Denis perinatal survey]

Goffinet F, Combiér E, Bucourt M, de Caunes F, Papiernik E.
J Gynecol Obstet Biol Reprod (Paris). 1996;25(2):153-9. French.

Injuries as a public health problem in sub-Saharan Africa: epidemiology and prospects for control.

Nordberg E.
East Afr Med J. 2000 Dec;77(12 Suppl):S1-43.

Reducing intrapartum-related deaths and disability: can the health system deliver?

Lawn JE, Kinney M, Lee AC, Chopra M, Donnay F, Paul VK, Bhutta ZA, Bateman M, Darmstadt GL.

Int J Gynaecol Obstet. 2009 Oct;107 Suppl 1:S123-40, S140-2. Review.

Changing patterns of perinatal death, 1982-2000: a retrospective cohort study.

Bell R, Glinianaia SV, Rankin J, Wright C, Pearce MS, Parker L.

Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed. 2004 Nov;89(6):F531-6.

Cause of death as a contemporary problem.

Rosenberg HM.

J Hist Med Allied Sci. 1999 Apr;54(2):133-53.

The pathology in perinatal mortality in Nairobi, Kenya.

Lucas SB, Mati JK, Aggarwal VP, Sanghvi H.

Bull Soc Pathol Exot Filiales. 1983 Nov;76(5):579-83.

Maternal risk factors for cause-specific stillbirth and neonatal death.

Winbo I, Serenius F, Dahlquist G, Källén B.

Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand. 2001 Mar;80(3):235-44.

Inquiries into perinatal and early childhood deaths in a health care district.

Brimblecombe F, Bastow M, Jones J, Kennedy N, Wadsworth J.

Arch Dis Child. 1984 Jul;59(7):682-7.

Perinatal mortality audit: counting, accountability, and overcoming challenges in scaling up in low- and middle-income countries.

Pattinson R, Kerber K, Waiswa P, Day LT, Mussell F, Asiruddin SK, Blencowe H, Lawn JE.

Int J Gynaecol Obstet. 2009 Oct;107 Suppl 1:S113-21, S121-2. Review.

Global report on preterm birth and stillbirth (4 of 7): delivery of interventions.

Victora CG, Rubens CE; GAPPS Review Group.

BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2010 Feb 23;10 Suppl 1:S4. Review.

Evaluation of the quality of cause of death statistics in rural China using verbal autopsies.

Wang L, Yang G, Jiemin M, Rao C, Wan X, Dubrovsky G, Lopez AD.

J Epidemiol Community Health. 2007 Jun;61(6):519-26.

[Classification of perinatal and neonatal deaths. Fetal, obstetrical and neonatal causes]

Andersen KV, Helweg-Larsen K, Lange AP.

Ugeskr Laeger. 1991 May 20;153(21):1494-7. Danish

Confidential regional enquiry into mature stillbirths and neonatal deaths--a multi-disciplinary peer panel perspective of the perinatal care of 238 deaths.

Tan KH, Wyldes MP, Settatee R, Mitchell T.

Singapore Med J. 1999 Apr;40(4):251-5

[Intrauterine death: experience at a tertiary centre of Italy]

Bastianelli C, Carrara S, Filippi V, Rapiti S, Ripani AE, Farris M.
Minerva Ginecol. 2007 Oct;59(5):505-11. Indonesian.

Evaluation of child deaths registration in a Jordanian community.

Al-Rabee K, Alkafajei A.
East Mediterr Health J. 2006 Jan-Mar;12(1-2):23-34.

Reclassification of unexplained stillbirths using clinical practice guidelines.

Headley E, Gordon A, Jeffery H.
Aust N Z J Obstet Gynaecol. 2009 Jun;49(3):285-9.

Perinatal mortality in rural India: a strategy for reduction through primary care. I Stillbirths.

Shah U, Pratinidhi AK, Bhatlawande PV.
J Epidemiol Community Health. 1984 Jun;38(2):134-7.

Towards an end to stillbirths.

Heazell AE.
BMJ. 2010 Oct 6;341:c5070. doi: 10.1136/bmj.c5070.

World Health Organisation, Technical Consultation on Postpartum and Postnatal Care, 2008, https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http://whqlibdoc.who.int/hq/2010/WHO_MPS_10.03_eng.pdf Accessed October 15-30, 2010.

World Health Organisation, Timor-Leste: National Expenditure On Health, (US Dollar), <https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http://www.who.int/entity/nha/country/tls.pdf> Accessed October 15-30, 2010.

Maternal mortality in 2005: estimates developed by WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, and the World Bank. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2007.

Pattinson RC, Buchmann E, Mantel G, Schoon M, Rees H. Can enquiries into severe acute maternal morbidity act as a surrogate for maternal death enquiries? *BJOG* 2003; 110: 889-93.

Say L, Pattinson RC, Gülmezoglu AM. WHO systematic review of maternal morbidity and mortality: the prevalence of severe acute maternal morbidity (near miss). *Reprod Health* 2004; 1: 3

Villar J, Valladares E, Wojdyla D, Zavaleta N, Carroli G, Velazco A, et al., et al. WHO 2005 global survey on maternal and perinatal health research group. Caesarean delivery rates and pregnancy outcomes: the 2005 WHO global survey on maternal and perinatal health in Latin America. *Lancet* 2006; 367: 1819-29

A, Faundes A, Machoki M, Bataglia V, Amokrane F, Donner A, et al., et al. Methodological considerations in implementing the WHO Global Survey for Monitoring Maternal and Perinatal Health. *Bull World Health Organ* 2008; 86: 126-31

Villar J, Carroli G, Zavaleta N, Donner A, Wojdyla D, Faundes A, et al., et al. World Health Organization 2005 Global Survey on Maternal and Perinatal Health Research Group. Maternal and neonatal individual risks and benefits associated with caesarean delivery: multicentre prospective study. *BMJ* 2007; 335: 1025-35

Souza JP, Cecatti JG, Parpinelli MA, Serruya SJ, Amaral E. Appropriate criteria for identification of near-miss morbidity in tertiary care facilities: a cross sectional study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 2007; 7: 20.

Mario R. Festin (et al), International survey on variations in practice of the management of the third stage of labour.

[https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http://whqlibdoc.who.int/bulletin/2003/Vol81-No4/bulletin_2003_81\(4\)_286-291.pdf](https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http://whqlibdoc.who.int/bulletin/2003/Vol81-No4/bulletin_2003_81(4)_286-291.pdf)

Won E, Ancona M, Carrigan K, Laverty B, Rhee P., Humanitarian Aid Mission in East Timor: Experiences of U.S. Naval Medical Services, *Mil Med.* 2006 Jan;171(1):29-36., Aviation Combat Element, Naval Medical Center San Diego, San Diego, CA 92134-1005, USA.

[i] Source WHO, Global Health Observatory <http://apps.who.int/ghodata/?vid=19600>

[ii] Timor-Leste: Health Statistics Report, 2006.

[iii] Source Family Health International <http://www.fhi.org/en/Topics/maternalmort.htm>

[iv] Source Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste Health Profile, August 2002.

[v] Source Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste, Health Profile, August 2002.

[vi] Source CIA World Fact Book Website

[vii] 2009

[viii] 5 Nepal Demographic and Health Surveys 2001 and 2006